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Designing a small OSWEC for PacWave South Test Site

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Abstract

Wave energy converters should be intentionally designed for the anticipated deployment conditions. As an example, this paper details the dynamics of an oscillating surge wave energy converter and the design strategy for the PacWave deployment site. Both the vertical location of the center of gravity and the generator power rating are found to impact the performance, with a lower center of gravity leading to better performance, and the generator power rating serving as a method for controlling capacity factor. Furthermore, an analysis of the performance assessment method (clustering and power matrix) identifies the intricacies of selecting an appropriate number of representative sea state clusters and the relationship with the the center of gravity and generator power rating. For the study completed, 4 clusters were sufficient to accurately discern performance trends.

Keywords: Wave energy conversion; Optimization; PacWave

1 Introduction

Wave energy converters (WECs) are commonly designed to perform best in specific wave conditions characteristic to the intended deployment site. The design can be curated to site conditions in a number of ways including tuning the device natural frequency [1] or assessing performance in a number of representative sea states (using a joint probability distribution or power matrices [2] or clustering methods [3]). Each of these methods has advantages and disadvantages: tuning the device natural frequency is simple but will not work well with influential PTO dynamics and/or when nonlinear dynamics are present, power matrices are accurate but computationally inefficient, and clustering methods can be more efficient but accuracy for WEC performance assessment has not been studied in detail.

Along with the method of designing for specific site conditions, it is vital to consider the full system dynamics including controls at all stages of design (control co-design). Control co-design has been applied to wave energy converters in a number of instances [4, 5], and can be particularly impactful when system dynamics are nonlinear [6]. For oscillating surge wave energy converters (OSWECs), the focus of this study, the dynamics can be highly nonlinear due to motion constraints [7].

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Figure 1: Dimensions of OSWEC used for this study (based on single flap of FOSWEC).

Table 1: Design parameters of the OSWEC system.

Parameter	Value
Height	0.58 m
Draft	0.46 m
Width (perpendicular to wave)	0.76 m
Thickness (parallel to wave) (bottom)	0.05 m
Thickness (parallel to wave) (top)	0.12 m
Mass	23.1 kg
Inertia (about center of gravity)	1.19 kgm ²
Center of gravity z-location (with respect to still water line)	-0.29 m
Gear ratio	3.75
Generator torque constant	6.7 Nm/A
Generator winding resistance	0.5 Ω

This paper applies control co-design to a small OSWEC for the PacWave marine energy testing site [8]. The center of gravity of the OSWEC and the generator/motor power rating and their respective impact on the converted electrical power and capacity factor are analyzed. Furthermore, the method of designing for specific site wave conditions (natural frequency, clustering, and joint probability distribution) is assessed relative to the design variables. Through this multi-variable study, an effective design process for wave energy conversion at the PacWave site is demonstrated as well as the intricacies of selecting an appropriate site performance characterization method.

This study is intended to be an initial analysis on the floating oscillating surge wave energy converter (FOSWEC) [9, 10, 11] which is characterized by a floating platform acting as a base for two oscillating flaps. The dimensions of one single flap of the FOSWEC were used as a baseline in this study. (detailed in Table 1 and shown in Figure 1). Similarly, the power take-off (PTO) parameters were initially designed to be the same from previous FOSWEC test campaigns, but it was found that the generator was insufficient for the PacWave conditions. Instead, the generator characteristics from the WaveBot [4] were used due to their improved performance in the larger wave conditions (while maintaining the same gear ratio as used by the FOSWEC). These PTO parameters are also detailed in Table 1.

2 WecOptTool

WecOptTool² is an open-source WEC optimization software that supports efficient PTO and control optimization. WecOptTool will be used to simulate the dynamics of the OSWEC (based on hydrodynamic coefficients from the

²WecOptTool: <https://github.com/sandialabs/WecOptTool>

Figure 2: Wave condition representation methods.

boundary element method (BEM) solver Capytaine³ [12]) in regular and irregular wave conditions and optimize the applied PTO force across the simulation time. WecOptTool uses a pseudo-spectral solution method [13, 4] to maintain time-dependent constraints, such as on the the WEC position and converted power, and maximize an arbitrary objective function. The optimal control trajectory from the pseudo-spectral method used is generally acausal, meaning it could not be applied in real-time, but it provides a great way to optimize the control trajectory without prescribing a fixed control structure which could significantly limit the design space [14].

The optimization problem is set up generally in (1), and more detail on the structure and setup can be found in [15].

$$\min_x J(x) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad r(x) = 0, \quad c_{ineq}(x) \geq 0, \quad c_{eq}(x) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Here, the state variable x consists of both the Fourier coefficients for the WEC position and the control coefficients defining the applied PTO force. $J(x)$ is the objective function (e.g., average electrical power), $r(x)$ captures the WEC dynamics in residual form, and c_{eq} and c_{ineq} are arbitrary equality and inequality constraints. In this study, the objective function is the average electrical power, and two inequality constraints are applied: one to limit the rotation of the WEC to 25° in either direction and another to limit the root mean square (RMS) value of the electrical power (as a proxy for the generator power rating). Using the pseudo-spectral method, WecOptTool can enforce the constraints while maximizing the converted electrical power over the entire simulation time concurrently [16].

3 Designing for PacWave

In order to design the system for deployment at PacWave, the wave conditions first need to be identified. Traditionally, this is done by creating an average annual energy table [17], while more recent approaches create a number of representative clusters [3]. For this study, the two approaches are compared as a method for characterizing the wave conditions and assessing the WEC performance. Figure 2 (a) shows the annual energy table, and the four clusters created using k-means clustering and the corresponding spectra are shown in Figure 2 (b).

3.1 Multi-variable study

The goal of this study is to consider two design variables: the center of gravity z-location and the generator's power rating. The rated power of the generator can be enforced by a constraint on the RMS electrical power. Through brief analysis, a range of reasonable values for the RMS power (4 - 40 W) and center of gravity (-0.42 - 0 m) were determined. First, a multi-variable parameter sweep was used to assess the impacts of these two design variables

³Capytaine: <https://ance11.in/capytaine/latest/>

(a) Average electrical power vs. RMS power constraint for a range of center of gravity locations in PacWave conditions.

(b) Average converted electrical power vs. capacity factor for a range of center of gravity locations in PacWave conditions.

Figure 3: Average electrical power as a function of other parameters.

on performance using the four representative waves from Figure 2 (b). The results of the multi-variable study are summarized in Figure 3 (a) and 3 (b) with the electrical power averaged across the four weighted sea states.

A lower RMS power constraint leads to a smaller average electrical power. This is not surprising: as the generator power rating is decreased, the electrical power that's able to be converted decreases. But, the decrease in electrical power is less extreme than the decrease in RMS power, meaning the capacity factor (defined as the ratio of converted electrical power to the RMS power constraint) increases as the RMS constraint is decreased. The RMS power constraint (therefore generator power rating) can effectively be used to control the capacity factor, and an efficient design is one in which the rated power of the generator is large enough to allow for significant electrical power conversion but also small enough to have a high power to cost ratio, represented here by an increased capacity factor.

When considering the vertical location of the center of gravity, it is clear that the lowest center of gravity case performs best across all RMS power constraint values in terms of both average electrical power and capacity factor. The largest difference in power versus center of gravity occurs for capacity factors between 0.5 and 0.7, where the result for all cases is impacted by the RMS power constraint, but the average electrical power is still relatively large.

3.2 Cluster convergence

When creating wave spectre from different clustering (defined along equally-spaced frequency array from 0.012 to 1.44 Hz), the amount of energy contained by the representative waves changes. More clusters leads to a more accurate measure of the total energy characteristic to the site (top plot of Figure 4). Although the energy flux is relatively inaccurate with a low number of clusters, it doesn't correspond directly to the accuracy of optimization results and design decisions. For example, if the relationship between the objective and the design variable is consistent regardless of the number of clusters, using 1 cluster would lead to the same design decision as 32 clusters.

To evaluate the importance of the number of clusters in terms of the optimization (and subsequent design decisions) as well as compare to the matrix approach, the impact on the result (average electrical power) across the ranges of design variables needs to be understood (bottom plot of Figure 4). It is clear that even though the energy flux is relatively inaccurate with a low number of clusters, the optimized average power can still be fairly accurate. This is an important finding suggesting that energy flux, which is commonly used to determine the number of clusters needed, may not be the determining factor. It is always important to consider the design problem at hand, but the less than 7% error with any number of clusters indicates that design decisions can be made relatively effectively with a low number of clusters. Looking at the different design variables in more detail, it can be seen that for loose RMS power constraints (e.g., 40 W), the center of gravity is not especially impactful to the number of clusters needed (although it does still impact the resultant power). On the other hand, for tight RMS power constraints (e.g., 4 W), a lower center of gravity (e.g., 0 m) significantly decreases the error for lower numbers of clusters. As the number of clusters is increased, a larger range of wave conditions are considered. This could explain why the average electrical power with a tight RMS constraint is greater at lower numbers of clusters even though the amount of power contained in those waves is

Figure 4: Top: As the number of clusters increase, the amount of energy flux included approaches the actual result (based on hourly data). Bottom: As the number of clusters increase, the resultant electrical power generally increases in accuracy. With a loose RMS power constraint (40 W) the trend is the same regardless of the center of gravity. With a tight RMS power constraint, the trend changes depending on the center of gravity. Note that 32 clusters is assumed to estimate the electrical power to 100% accuracy.

smaller. The low number of clusters represents a range of waves where the performance is less limited by the constraint when compared to the wider range of wave considered by the 32 cluster set. With tighter RMS power constraints, the constraint will be more active and have a greater impact on the results. For the lower center of gravity case with the tight RMS power constraints, it is likely that the constraint are especially limiting across the range of sea states leading to very consistent results. Because the trend in the average power error is very similar for both centers of gravity when RMS power is set to 40 W, it is okay to consider a relatively low number of clusters when characterizing the performance with a high generator power rating. Regardless of the number of clusters, the relative difference between two results will be consistent. On the other hand, with tight RMS power constraints, the inconsistency in the convergence of power with respect to the number of clusters suggests the importance of using more clusters to represent the wave conditions when designing for a low generator power rating.

The clustering method is generally preferred to the power matrix for optimization both for its general ability to represent all waves by a smaller number of representative sea states (more efficient computation) and its smaller range of representative sea states. While a power matrix considers all extents within a range of wave heights and periods (even when they are very low probability), the clustering methods generally result in clusters around only relatively common wave conditions. By reducing the range of sea states for which to optimize, potential scaling and convergence issues, which are more likely when attempting to cater to a large range of results, can be mitigated. The power matrix results are not displayed in this study precisely for this reason: convergence results were inconsistent across sea states using the power matrix approach. Future studies will address the convergence issues to further investigate the trade-offs between the power matrix and clustering approaches.

4 Conclusions

To be most effective, wave energy converter designs must accurately consider relevant conditions in which they will be deployed. This can be especially true when nonlinear dynamics are present such as for an OSWEC with tight rotational motion constraints. In this study, both the vertical location of the center of gravity and the rated power of the generator/motor are found to significantly impact the studied OSWEC's performance. For the PacWave site, a lower center of gravity can be used to improve performance across all RMS power constraint values, and by constraining the RMS power, which relates closely to the generator power rating, we are able to investigate different solutions which trade off average power vs. capacity factor. In terms of the assessment method (modeled wave conditions), the accuracy of the results increases with the number of sea state clusters. But, in this study, with loose RMS power constraints (high generator power rating), 4 clusters were sufficient to accurately discern performance trends.

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